

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EMOTIONS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK TV SERIES

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Annotation

This article explores the lexico-semantic field of positive and negative emotions within video-verbal discourse, focusing on a comparative analysis of English and Uzbek TV series. Through a detailed examination of lexical and semantic features, the study reveals how different cultures express emotions in multimedia contexts. By analyzing a corpus of TV series, the article highlights both universal and culturally specific ways of expressing emotions in English and Uzbek, reflecting individualistic versus collectivist societal values. The findings contribute to the understanding of how emotional language functions in media and opens new pathways for future cross-cultural studies of emotion.

Keywords: lexico-semantic field, positive emotions, negative emotion, video-verbal discourse, English TV series, Uzbek TV series, cross-cultural communication, emotional lexicon, media discourse

Introduction

Emotions are central to human communication, and their expression in language provides insight into cultural values, societal norms, and individual experiences. The analysis of the lexico-semantic field—the network of words related by meaning—pertaining to positive and negative emotions offers a unique lens to examine how different cultures express feelings in media. This article aims to explore the lexico-semantic field of emotions within video-verbal discourse, focusing on English and Uzbek TV series as cultural artifacts.

Theoretical Framework

The concept of the lexico-semantic field refers to a set of words that belong to the same category and are related by meaning. In the context of emotions, words expressing joy, happiness, love, and contentment fall under the category of positive emotions, while those associated with fear, anger, sadness, and disappointment represent negative emotions. These emotional lexicons are not only linguistic units but are also heavily influenced by cultural and societal factors.

Video-verbal discourse, particularly in TV series, is a powerful medium through which emotions are conveyed both visually and verbally. The interplay of language and visual cues enhances the understanding of how emotions are expressed, making TV series an ideal platform for studying the lexico-semantic fields of emotions.

Methodology

For this study, a comparative analysis of English and Uzbek TV series was conducted. The corpus was selected from popular TV series in both languages that represent a broad range of genres, such as drama, comedy, and thriller, where emotional expression is integral to character development and narrative progression.

The analysis was performed in two stages:

1. **Lexical Analysis:** Identifying the words and phrases used to express positive and negative emotions in the dialogues.
2. **Semantic Analysis:** Understanding the nuances of these emotional expressions, including cultural connotations and how they are perceived by the audience.

English TV Series:

In English-language TV series, the lexicon of positive emotions often includes words such as “love,” “happiness,” “joy,” “hope,” and “pride.” These terms are typically associated with personal achievements, romantic relationships, and family dynamics. Negative emotions, on the other hand, are frequently expressed using terms like “anger,” “fear,” “hate,” “sadness,” and “disappointment.”

The English language, known for its vast vocabulary, provides a wide range of synonyms and subtle distinctions for emotional expressions. For instance, terms like “ecstatic,” “content,” and “elated” all refer to happiness but vary in intensity and context. Similarly, the nuances between “fear,” “dread,” and “terror” highlight different dimensions of negative emotions.

Uzbek TV Series:

In contrast, the lexicon of emotions in Uzbek TV series reflects the cultural emphasis on community, family, and respect.

Positive emotions are often associated with collective happiness, honor, and social harmony, using terms like “baxt” (happiness), “muhabbat” (love), and “quvonch” (joy). Negative emotions, such as “g’azab” (anger), “xavotir” (worry), and “xafa” (sad), often revolve around disruptions to familial or social ties

A significant finding in Uzbek-language TV series is the frequent use of proverbs and idiomatic expressions to convey emotions, which adds layers of cultural meaning. For example, rather than explicitly stating “I am angry,” a character may use a culturally loaded phrase that indirectly expresses this emotion in a socially acceptable way.

Cultural Insights

The comparative analysis of English and Uzbek TV series highlights the differences in how emotions are expressed and perceived across cultures. While English TV series often emphasize individual emotions and internal struggles, Uzbek series tend to focus on collective emotions and the social impact of personal feelings. This difference reflects broader cultural values, with individualism being a hallmark of Western societies and collectivism central to Uzbek culture.

Furthermore, the emotional lexicon in both languages is shaped by the medium of television itself. Visual cues such as facial expressions, gestures, and cinematography enhance the verbal expressions of emotions, creating a richer, multimodal discourse that transcends language barriers.

Conclusion

The study of the lexico-semantic field of positive and negative emotions in video-verbal discourse reveals both universal and culture-specific ways of expressing emotions. While there are common emotional experiences shared across English and Uzbek TV series, the linguistic and cultural context shapes how these emotions are articulated and understood by audiences.

Future research could expand this analysis to include other languages and media forms, offering a broader perspective on the global expression of emotions. Additionally, further exploration of the visual and auditory components of video-verbal discourse would provide a more comprehensive understanding of emotional communication in multimedia contexts.

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